

Experimental characterization of evaporation heat exchangers using low Global Warming Potential fluids

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Abstract

The present work aims at presenting the selection of the most appropriate measurement techniques that will be used to study the two-phase flow distribution of an air/water mixture inside the channels of an adiabatic heat exchanger. The first results for the calibration and the use of these techniques are also presented.

Keywords: Gas-liquid two-phase flow, multiphase flow metering, experimental

1. Introduction

Vapor cycle systems are closed loops that can be used for equipment cooling and environmental control purposes such as air conditioning. They are composed of several key components (compressor, condenser, expansion valve,...), among which evaporators are continuously subjects of research to improve their efficiency by reducing their volume and increasing their overall aerothermal performances. One straightforward way to improve the heat exchange is to improve the flow distribution among the different channels of the evaporator. Indeed, flow misdistribution of the inlet two-phase fluid can cause up to 30% of thermal losses [1]. Commonly, high Global Warming Potential (GWP) refrigerants like R134a are used as fluids [2] [3] [4], meaning that their behavior, when it comes to flow distribution in the header and channels, is well characterized and rather predictable. However, their use is already strictly regulated for domestic use or other industrial applications. Eventhough it does not yet apply for the aeronautical field, research is currently undergoing in this industry to explore the low GWP refrigerants in order to reduce the environmental impact of aircrafts. The present work is part

of the exPerimental And Numerical mulTiscale mulTiphasic Heat ExchangeR (PANTTHER) Clean Sky 2 project, which will aim at studying and characterizing the behavior of the low GWP refrigerants like R1234ze for which research works focused mainly so far on simpler geometries [5] [6], as well as improving the flow distribution in the evaporator header. The Von Karman Institute is in charge of the experimental approach. To do so, two experimental test benches will be constructed: one transparent adiabatic to develop and validate the methods for the distribution improvement and the measurement techniques chosen, and a full-scale diabatic one. One fundamental objective of this work will also be the better understanding and prediction of the flow patterns transitions in two-phase flows. This paper deals with the first adiabatic test facility.

During the first year of the project, the main parameters influencing the flow maldistribution were gathered and analyzed, to decide whether they could be expected to have a major or minor impact. It was also noticed that most studies in the literature focus on one specific parameter or sometimes a couple of them, but very few studies exist about the impact of a combination of several parameters. Thereby, in a

second time, the adiabatic test bench was designed to be able to reach this objective. Besides, the required air and water flow conditions were calculated to be in flow similarity with a low GWP refrigerant by mean of three two-phase flow variables, but also to take into account the project requirements in terms of mass flow rates and maximum dimensions. In a third time, a literature review about the multiphase flow metering was achieved, to select the appropriate two-phase flow measurement techniques required for the monitoring of the mass-flow rates, the void fraction, the quality and the pressure at several locations of the facility. This work will be firstly presented in the section 2, as well as the main correlations cited in the literature for the prediction of the pressure and the void fraction. The experimental results obtained so far are shown in the section 4 and discussed.

2. Literature review

To be able to measure accurately the flow distribution among the channels, a strong literature review was achieved in a first time about the existing measurement techniques suited for a two-phase flow. Due to the complexity of a flow involving two phases, selecting the most appropriate combination of techniques is not an easy task. In a second time, due to the selection of a void fraction measurement technique through differential pressure measurement, the main predictive correlations for the pressure drops in a two-phase flow were gathered.

2.1. Multiphase flow metering

Multiphase flow metering can be defined as a mean to obtain, through a combination of instruments, the flow rates of the two individual phases. Depending on the mass flow rates of the gas and the liquid phase, the structure of the flow will be different. However, it should be noted that the instruments used for multiphase flow metering are very sensitive to the flow patterns in the channel, and this is the main reason why two-phase flow measurements are so difficult to perform [7; 8]. Since no instrument is able to determine both individual flow rates, several devices have to be combined. In multiphase flow metering, the instruments can measure five basic parameters: density, velocity, momentum, void fraction and mass flow. Since various devices exist for each category, only the most relevant for the present project will be presented in the next sections.

2.1.1. Coriolis flowmeter

To measure both the density and the total mass flow at the same time, a Coriolis flow meter can be used [9; 7]. The Coriolis flow meter consists in using a bent pipe that is vibrating at his resonant frequency. If a fluid is flowing inside the pipe, its inertia alternately reinforces and resists the oscillations that are imposed in the tube to cause the twist. The tube distortions, evaluated electronically by optimally located sensors, will allow to directly determine the mass flow rate by measuring the phase shift between the sensors. In addition, the resonance frequency at which the tube is vibrating depends on the tube geometry, material, but also mass of the medium vibrating in the tube. Therefore, monitoring the change in the resonance frequency of the pipe will allow the determination of the fluid density.

2.1.2. Venturi flowmeter

Venturi flowmeter are also often found in studies for two-phase flow metering of the total mass-flow in which case a correlation has to be used to estimate the total density of the flow [10; 11], and is a type of head flowmeter, which is based on the Bernoulli equation. The flow meter consists in placing a restriction in the flow, which will increase the velocity and decrease the static pressure. The total mass flow is obtained in a two phase flow, the same way as in a single phase flow, meaning that the flow rate is determined through the measurement of the pressure difference upstream the venturi and in the throat ΔP , providing the diameter ratio β , discharge coefficient C , the compressibility and thermal expansion factors contained in K are known [12].

$$m_{TP} = \frac{C}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^4}} K \sqrt{2\Delta P \rho_{TP}} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P \rho_{TP}} \quad (1)$$

The two-phase flow density is then approximated by multiple correlations that have been developed since the 90's. These correlations are usually based on a weighted average of the vapor and liquid phase densities and on the quality. Hence, the values of the coefficients can be easily adapted to fit the results from a specific design and different fluids [13]. The correlations that will be used for comparison with the measurement data in the section 4 are listed in the table 1.

These venturi flowmeters are very often coupled in the literature with void fraction meter such as capacitance probe [12] for two main reasons. The first one is because the void fraction is used in the calculation

Table 1: Venturi correlations

Correlation name	Equation
Homogeneous [14]	$\dot{m}_{TP} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P / \left(\frac{x}{\rho_v} + \frac{1-x}{\rho_l} \right)}$
Chisholm [15]	$\dot{m}_{TP} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P \rho_l} / \left[(1-x) \sqrt{1 + \frac{C}{X} + \frac{1}{X^2}} \right]$ <p style="text-align: center;">with $X = \sqrt{\rho_v / \rho_l} \frac{(1-x)}{x}$ and $C = (\rho_v / \rho_l)^{0.25} + (\rho_l / \rho_v)^{0.25}$ when $X < 1$ and $C = (\rho_v / \rho_l)^{0.5} + (\rho_l / \rho_v)^{0.5}$ when $X \geq 1$</p>
Zhang et al. [16]	$\dot{m}_{TP} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P \rho_l} / \sqrt{\left[x^{1.25+0.25x^{1/3}} \right] \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_v} - 1 \right) + 1}$
Zhang et al. [17]	$\dot{m}_{TP} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P \rho_l} / \sqrt{c \left(\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \right)^n \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_v} \right)^m + 1}$ $= c' \left(\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \right) \left(\frac{\rho_v}{\rho_l} \right)^H = \frac{\sqrt{\Delta P_l}}{\sqrt{\Delta P_g}}$ <p style="text-align: center;">with c, n, m, c' and H which are flow pattern depending constants and are equal to 0.50, 0.95, 0.02, 0.51 and 0.65 respectively for bubbly and slug patterns</p>
Murdock [18]	$\dot{m}_{TP} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P} / \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{\rho_v}} + M \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{\rho_l}} \right)$ with M=1.26
Lin [19]	$\dot{m}_{TP} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P} / \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{\rho_v}} + \theta \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{\rho_l}} \right)$ <p style="text-align: center;">With $\theta = 1.48625 - 9.26541 \left(\frac{\rho_v}{\rho_l} \right) + 44.6954 \left(\frac{\rho_v}{\rho_l} \right)^2 - 60.6150 \left(\frac{\rho_v}{\rho_l} \right)^3$ $- 5.12966 \left(\frac{\rho_v}{\rho_l} \right)^4 - 26.5743 \left(\frac{\rho_v}{\rho_l} \right)^5$</p>
Philipps [20]	$\dot{m}_{TP} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P} / \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{\rho_v}} + M \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{\rho_l}} \right)$ with M=1.5
James [21]	$\dot{m}_{TP} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P} / \left(\frac{x^n}{\sqrt{\rho_v}} + \frac{(1-x)^n}{\sqrt{\rho_l}} \right)$ with n=1.5
Collins [22]	$\dot{m}_{TP} = K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P} / \left(a \frac{x}{\sqrt{\rho_v}} + b \frac{1-x}{\sqrt{\rho_l}} + c \frac{\sqrt{x(1-x)}}{\sqrt{\rho_l \rho_v}} \right)^{1/4}$ <p style="text-align: center;">with a,b, and c to be defined experimentally</p>

of the quality, required for the correlations as stated above. These two quantities are related by mean of a calibration. The second one is because the calibration of the venturi depends on the flow patterns, which can be retrieved from the data clustering of the void fraction meter signal as will be explained in the section 2.1.5.

2.1.3. Capacitance probe

The capacitance probes are the most widely used for the determination of the void fraction, but their output signals can also be used for flow pattern identification. These instruments are also referred as impedance probes in the literature. The impedance probe is a volume-averaged void fraction meter. The working principle is based on the fact that the impedance between two electrodes facing each other on a channel can be related to the change of conductivity or capacitivity in the medium, and thus to the void fraction, through a calibration curve. Many designs

exist for the electrodes, whether of concave shapes (Fig. 1, parallel symmetrical or asymmetrical plate shapes, or helicoidal [23]). The number of electrodes can also differ from only two (a low-potential one and a high-potential one), up to eight alternating between a high and low potential electrodes and creating a rotating field. A major issue of this probe is that it can be very sensitive to the flow pattern inside the channel for some designs, while for other the influence seems to be minor, especially when at least 6 electrodes are used [12; 7]. If the flow regime is found to influence the output signal, several calibration curves will have to be obtained, at least one for the annular and the stratified flow patterns, and ideally one for each pattern.

2.1.4. Dual optical probe

Another void fraction measuring instrument that can be cited is the optical probe, that is part of a wider section of intrusive measurement techniques named

Figure 1: Concave capacitance probe design [24]

needle probes which are mainly found for liquid/gas applications [25]. The working principle of this instrument relies on the change of refractive index in the measured medium, between the liquid and the gaseous phase. Light is emitted in the sensor until the end of the probe tip located inside the channel. Whether the sensor is surrounded by gas or liquid, the light will be reflected (due to the low optical index of the gaseous phase) and thus send back to the acquisition system to be converted into an electrical signal or not reflected (Fig. 2). Hence, this is a very local void fraction measurement which does not require any prior calibration.

Figure 2: Optical probe principle [25]

2.1.5. Flow pattern identification

The most common way to characterize the flow pattern in a channel was originally by visualizations [8]. However, since this method depends upon the appreciation of an operator, it is thus very subjective, and there is a lack of clear and quantitative criteria to discriminate the flow regimes transitions. Over the last three decades, more and more studies tend to determine the flow patterns based on the data clustering or classification of probe signals, in an attempt to obtain more objective and reliable experimental data and thus to be able to model more precisely the flow transitions. Most of the studies employ signals coming from capacitance/conductance probes and from differential or absolute pressure taps measurements [26; 27; 28; 29].

The flow regimes are often determined by analysing the Power Spectral Density or the Probability Density Function of the signal. This method relies on the principle that each pattern has a "flow regime signature" [8] (Fig. 3), which means that for each regime, the combination of the fluctuations and of the average value of the signal is specific. The data clustering or classification of signals has been proven over the last decades to be able to predict efficiently the flow patterns. Besides, it is now supported by a numerous amount of studies in the literature [25].

Figure 3: Flow regime signature examples [8]

2.2. Pressure drops and void fraction correlations

Like for any other system, it is important to be able to predict the pressure drops as well the heat transfer that will be created by the boiling two-phase flow in the evaporator for three main reasons: to know the pump power required, to verify that the global pressure drops do not exceed a certain limitation usually fixed ahead of the sizing process and on the other hand to verify that the minimum required heat transferred from one fluid to the other one is reached. Several model exist for the pressure drops [30; 31] that are either based on a homogeneous assumption (meaning zero slip condition: both phase flow at the same velocity), or on a separated flow assumption. The main models that can be found in the literature: Lockhart - Martinelli [32], Chisholm [33], Friedel [34] and Müller-Steinhagen and Heck [35].

However, the pressure drops correlations are highly depending on the flow patterns. The range of flow conditions and especially of flow patterns for which the correlations are accurate is not well documented by their authors, making the choice of the most suitable correlation difficult.

To be able to predict the pressure drops, the void fraction has to be either measured or predicted also thanks to a correlation. Márquez-Torres et al. [36] realized a great review of 63 void fraction correlations that they compared with 11 895 experimental points to determine if one single equation could predict all the corresponding void fractions. Their work led to the conclusion that none of the existing correlation was sufficient to accurately predict the void fraction over a wide range of operating conditions. They also presented a very interesting schematic summary of the best correlation to calculate the void fraction knowing the pipe orientation and the flow pattern studied or the fluid viscosity.

3. Experimental facility

A rather common experimental facility was constructed at the Von Karman Institute (VKI) to test (Fig. 4), select and calibrate the appropriate instruments to be used for a more complex test bench. The void fraction was measured in a 29.7mm smooth pipe diameter. The fluid studied consisted in a two-phase flow of an air-water mixture. A quality of up to 0.23 was reached as well as a void fraction of 0.8. The mass flow rate of water ranged from 0 to 12 L/min while the flow rate of air covered the range from 0 to 0.0235kg/s. A schematic of the set-up can be found on the figure 4. Water is pumped from a tank by a centrifugal pump (Wilo) and its flow rate is measured by mean of electromagnetic flowmeter (Fuji Electric). A 15-bar compressed air line is connected to the facility and its pressure is then decreased to 0.5-0.8 bar. The air flow rate is measured thanks to a thermal massflow sensor (CS Instruments). Air and water are mixed and then sent to a 60 pipe diameters straight length to ensure a fully developed flow at the inlet of the test section, which consists in a 1m long horizontal smooth pipe made of Plexiglass and of 20mm diameter, on which a capacitance probe is mounted for the "void fraction line", and in a 1m long horizontal plexiglass smooth pipe of 10mm diameter and connected the venturi flowmeter for the "venturi line". Visualizations of the flow patterns in the test section are achieved by mean a high-speed camera (Dantec). Two taps distanced by 1.5m from each other are connected to two pressure membrane sensors (Valydine) to monitor the pressure inside the pipe and to retrieve the void fraction. The air-water mixture is further sent to a Coriolis flowmeter (Yokogawa) to obtain the total mass flow rate and to the dual optical probe. The tests were carried at

a very low overpressure above the atmospheric pressure.

Figure 4: Facility for the calibration and test of the different instruments

The second step was to understand how to measure the flow distribution among all the channels and which quantity needed to be evaluated to do so. Based on the literature study several measurement techniques were found to be relevant: capacitance probe for the void fraction measurement, coupled with a venturi flow meter calibrated by mean of a Coriolis flowmeter, flow pattern recognition based on pressure signal data clustering [12; 13] and a dual optical probe to be able to relate the void fraction and the quality. The Venturi was designed at the VKI and based on the standard NFENISO5167-4 that defines how to calculate all the characteristic dimensions. Concerning the capacitance probe design, two leads were followed. The first one consisted in selecting a design from the literature that was sufficiently documented to be able to run electrostatic simulations, and designed for a mixture of air and water. The concave design from the work of Caniere et al. [24] was selected. The second solution was to test a capacitance probe designed at the VKI by a former PhD [37] for air and water with asymmetric parallel plates.

The optical probe was manufactured by the company RBI and equipped of two 30 microns tips of Sapphire, which enables also the obtention of the bubble size and velocity. The last void fraction calculation to be tested is derived from the pressure measurements [38].

4. Results

4.1. Flow patterns

Firstly, the flow patterns obtained in the 20mm diameter line were compared with the predictions of the flow map of Lin et al. [39] for almost the same pipe diameter.

Figure 5: Flow regimes compared with the transition predictions from Lin et al. [39]

It appears from the figure 5 that the flow patterns obtained by visualizations and from observations of the high-speed camera images fitted very well the flow map of Lin et al. apart for the intermittent/pseudo-slug regime that was found to start at earlier vapor velocity.

Secondly, the pressure drops obtained from the two taps and for tests from different days were measured and analyzed (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Pressure drops as a function of air velocity in the test section

Figure 7: Pressure drops as a function of water velocity in the test section

It can be straightforwardly understood from the graph why the choice of a predictive correlation can

be difficult and why a unique correlation can hardly cover all the flow patterns.

4.2. Dual optical probe

To evaluate the void fraction, measurements using a dual optical probe were achieved as explained in the section 3, and were compared with several correlations available in the literature. The results from this experimental campaign are presented in the figure 8.

Figure 8: Void fraction measurements by mean of a dual optical probe and comparison with model predictions

It can be seen that the void fraction is well predicted by two distinct correlations depending on the flow regimes. At low quality, and thus for bubbly or plug flow regimes, the Barcozy correlation [40] is the best fitting of the results. At higher quality, and for slug to intermittent or annular flow patterns, the results are in between the Wallis and the Zivi predictions [41; 42].

However, most correlations can be summarized in a common equation defined by Butterworth [13].

$$\alpha = \left[1 + k_0 \left(\frac{1-x}{x} \right)^{k_1} \left(\frac{\rho_v}{\rho_l} \right)^{k_2} \left(\frac{\mu_l}{\mu_v} \right)^{k_3} \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where x is the quality, ρ_l and ρ_v are the liquid and vapor densities, μ_l and μ_v are the liquid and vapor viscosities and k_0 , k_1 , k_2 and k_3 are the fitting parameters. The experimental data were fitted using this relationship and the result is presented in the figure 9 as well as the different coefficients.

The fitting by the Butterworth correlation gives a good result and the coefficients will be used later on in the project to obtain the quality, knowing the void fraction that will be provided by the capacitance probe.

4.3. Venturi flowmeter

The final results obtained so far concern the 10mm diameter line in which the venturi is implemented.

Figure 9: Void fraction measurements by mean of a dual optical probe fitted by the Butterworth correlation

The discharge coefficient C of the venturi (Eq. 1) was evaluated by mean of a water single-phase flow measurement and is found to be worth around 0.925 ± 0.1 (due to the diameter throat uncertainties), which is, eventhough a bit low, a reasonable value according to the literature [43]. Several correlations gathered from the literature review and presented in the section 2.1.2 were used to calculate the mass-flow rate in the venturi from the pressure drop measurements. The results are compared with the total mass flow rate obtained from the Coriolis flow meter.

Figure 10: Coriolis mass-flow rates compared with Venturi mass flow rates obtained with several correlations

It can be seen that the Chisholm [44] correlation gives very promising results, while the Murdock [18] and James [14] give reasonable results but not over the whole range. However, these two correlations as well as the one from Collins [22], rely on coefficients that can be modified and fitted to specific data but also for each flow pattern as done by Meng et al. [13].

The same work on the present data is shown in the figure 11 as long with the coefficients obtained when the Collins correlation is used for the fitting.

The flow patterns below a quality value of 0.1 comprise the Plug/Slug/Intermittent, while above 0.1, only the annular pattern is found. It can be noticed that the fitting of the results gives good results, but that two

Figure 11: $K_{geo} \sqrt{\Delta P} / m_{tot}$ fitted by the Collins correlation [22] as the function of the quality x

trends exist in the two groups of flow patterns. Thus, the two groups could be fitted separately but it would also be interesting to fill the gap between a quality of 0.075 and 0.15 to verify if the values of the coefficients are also valid in that zone.

5. Conclusion

The full characterization of a two phase flow through the measurement of the main parameters is a complex task due to the diversity of the instruments and their possible combination. A literature review of the relevant probes for the present study is presented, as well as the main correlations that will be used for the comparison. The experimental results obtained with an air/water mixture flow are presented and a new correlation for a 30mm diameter pipe between the void fraction and the inlet quality is given. The designed Venturi flowmeter is found to be a relevant instrument for air/water mass flow rate measurements and the calibration curve obtained from the adaptation of existing correlations is presented.

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